

Knowledge, Attitude and Practice Towards Risk Factors of Hypertension Among Outpatients at BMC Hospital

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ABSTRACT

In many developing nations, hypertension is becoming a rising public health issue. However, the awareness of hypertension among BMC Hospital patients has not yet been examined. As a result, the purpose of this study is to analyse outpatients' knowledge, attitude, and practice about hypertension risk factors at BMC Hospital. Controlling hypertension requires a patient's education, attitude, and practice. The study's findings will give information that may be utilised to establish long-term strategies for educating patients and the community about the negative health consequences of hypertension. During the data collecting period, the target population comprised of outpatients seeking treatment at BMC Hospital. The outpatient department of BMC Hospital sees around 24,515 people each year. The sample size for this study was calculated using the Cochran method for a single cross-sectional survey, yielding a sample size of 340 BMC Hospital outpatients. Face-to-face structured questionnaires were provided to all participants at the outpatient department to collect data. SPSS was used to enter and analyse the data. The prevalence of hypertension was assessed, and hypertension knowledge, attitude, and practices, including hypertension thresholds, risk factors, and complications, were examined. The lifestyle variables related with hypertension were investigated using logistic regression analysis, which yielded odds ratios and 95% confidence intervals. A p 0.05 significance level was judged statistically significant. The BMC Hospital's ethics committee authorized this investigation, and all study participants provided written informed permission. The analysis comprised data from 272 outpatients after data quality checks and missing data elimination. 77 (28.3%) of them were between the ages of 26 and 35. The majority of respondents (63.2%) were women, married (66.2%), and lived in rural regions (76.1%). The prevalence of hypertension was determined to be 22.1% at BMC Hospital. The study found a clear tendency of decreasing understanding of hypertension risk factors, with 216 (79.4%) individuals expressing limited knowledge of hypertension risk factors. Only 23.2% of patients were aware that stress or worry might raise their chance of developing hypertension. However, 44.9% of respondents had a positive opinion towards the need of stress reduction, lifestyle adjustments, frequent medication, and regular blood pressure measurement as hypertension prevention methods is emphasized.

Keywords: hypertension, knowledge, attitude, practice, risk factors, outpatients, BMC Hospital, public health, prevalence.

Cite as:

INTRODUCTION

The goal of this study was to look at outpatients at BMC Hospital's knowledge, attitude, and practise about hypertension risk factors. Hypertension is a substantial independent risk factor for cardiovascular disease and stroke in both developed and developing nations (Lozano et al., 2012; Rohla et al., 2016). The bulk of the global burden of cardiovascular disease mortality is borne by low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) (Lopez et al., 2006). Because of long-term treatment costs and productivity losses, noncommunicable diseases (NCDs), notably cardiovascular disease, pose a significant danger to global economic development (Bloom DE, 2011). NCDs are expected to outnumber communicable diseases as the leading cause of death in LMICs by 2030 (Mathers & Loncar, 2006). The most common is hypertension.

Hypertension is the most common kind of cardiovascular illness, accounting for half of all chronic disease costs, including psychiatric issues, diabetes, heart disease, and asthma. Hypertension, often known as high blood pressure, is a worldwide health problem that affects both industrialised and developing countries. It is a significant independent risk factor for a variety of health problems, including cardiovascular disease and stroke (Lozano et al., 2012). Several studies have shown hypertension as a substantial risk factor for poor health outcomes (Lozano et al., 2012; Rohla et al., 2016). LMICs endure a disproportionate share of the burden of hypertension-related health issues and death (Lopez et al., 2006). particularly hypertension, represent a significant threat to global economic growth due to long-term treatment costs and productivity damage (Bloom DE, 2011). NCDs are anticipated to outnumber communicable illnesses in prevalence in LMICs by 2030 (Mathers & Loncar, 2006). As the most frequent kind of NCD, hypertension poses a significant challenge to healthcare systems. Hypertension, sometimes known as the "silent killer," commonly remains untreated due to its asymptomatic nature (WHO, 2013). According to the World Health Organisation, over 972 million people worldwide had hypertension in 2000, with the majority living in poor countries (WHO, 2013). This number is expected to rise to 1.5 billion by 2025 (WHO, 2013). Globally, the prevalence of hypertension varies significantly by region. More than 40% of people aged 25 and over were diagnosed with hypertension in 2008, a significant increase from 600 million in 1980 to 1 billion in 2008 (WHO, 2011). The African Region has the greatest incidence of hypertension, affecting 46% of people aged 25 and above, while the Americas have the lowest, at 35% (WHO, 2011).

The rising incidence of hypertension in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) is intimately connected to socioeconomic developments and the "nutrition transition" that goes hand in hand with poverty reduction initiatives (Kuller, 2007). Urbanisation and accompanying lifestyle changes, such as food choices and decreased physical activity among urban dwellers with a medium to high socioeconomic class, contribute to the transition from communicable to noncommunicable illnesses in the population. Age, gender, ethnic origin, food, stress, sedentary lifestyle, urbanisation, family history, blood cholesterol, diabetes mellitus, and pre-existing vascular illnesses are all well-established risk factors for hypertension (de Ramirez et al., 2010).

The movement of people from rural to urban regions has intensified the burden of hypertension, sometimes known as "the burden of civilization." Obesity, smoking, decreased physical activity, excessive alcohol consumption, and hyperglycemia are common among people with a medium to high socioeconomic status and are linked to increased life expectancy, urbanisation, and the lifestyle changes that come with economic progress in developing countries (Akinlua et al., 2015). Finally, hypertension is a major public health issue over the world. Understanding the risk factors for hypertension and measuring outpatients' knowledge, attitude, and practises is critical for establishing successful methods to educate patients and improve community awareness. By analysing these characteristics in outpatients at BMC Hospital, this study hopes to collect vital information that may be used to develop long-term

strategies for educating patients and the community about the harmful health implications of hypertension.

Background

A prior study among 100 persons aged 27 to 67 years at an urban tertiary education institution discovered 36 hypertension participants, yielding a crude prevalence of 36%. Only 3% of individuals polled were aware of their hypertension, whereas 33% were not (Banyangiriki & Phillips, 2013). The increased prevalence of hypertension is cause for concern. Assessment of knowledge, attitudes, and practises (KAP) is an important component of hypertension control, but there is little evidence available from developing countries, where hypertension has only just been acknowledged as a severe health problem. As a result, the present study will investigate BMC Hospital outpatients' knowledge, attitudes, and practises addressing hypertension risk factors.

Problem Statements

The rising frequency of hypertension in BMC is a major source of worry. Knowledge, attitudes, and practises (KAP) assessment is a critical component of hypertension control, but little information is available of hospitals, where hypertension has just been identified as a serious health concern. As a result, the current study will look into patients' knowledge, attitudes, and practises regarding hypertension risk factors at BMC Hospital.

In BMC, like in other developing nations undergoing the epidemiological shift from communicable to noncommunicable chronic illnesses, hypertension has become a substantial concern (Tibazarwa & Damasceno, 2014). The emergence of hypertension as a public health problem in these countries is strongly linked to population ageing, urbanisation, and socioeconomic changes that favour sedentary habits, obesity, alcohol consumption, and salt intake, among other things (Bener & Saleh, 2013; Tavassoli et al., 2011). Many research have shown that knowledge and attitudes about risk factors, as well as healthy living practises, are linked to mortality (Oguoma et al., 2014; Tibazarwa & Damasceno, 2014). Many research have shown that knowledge and attitudes about NCDs and risk factors, as well as healthy living practices, are linked to CVD morbidity and mortality (Oguoma et al., 2014; Tibazarwa & Damasceno, 2014). Many research have revealed the influence of poor information, attitudes, and practise about hypertension and its prevalence. A KAP research on hypertension in Seychelles found that participants had high knowledge but poor attitudes and practises towards healthy living (Aubert et al., 1998).

There is a poor degree of awareness about hypertension. According to one study done, more than 33% of people lacked adequate understanding regarding hypertension (Banyangiriki & Phillips, 2013). There have been no studies on the knowledge, attitude, and practise of hypertension among outpatients in BMC hospitals. As a result, the current study would analyse outpatients' knowledge, attitude, and practises about hypertension risk factors in BMC Hospital.

Objective

- To measure outpatients' awareness of hypertension at BMC Hospital
- To assess outpatients' attitudes regarding hypertension control, treatment, and prevention at BMC Hospital
- To investigate the lifestyle practices of outpatients at BMC Hospital regarding hypertension risk factors.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The purpose of this literature study is to better understand the knowledge, attitudes, and practises of outpatients at BMC Hospital about hypertension risk factors. The review includes theoretical and empirical literature, critical analysis, and identification of research gaps, theoretical and conceptual frameworks, and essential summary points.

Hypertension, a serious cardiovascular disease, is an increasing public health problem worldwide. It is significantly linked to issues such as ageing populations, urbanization, sedentary lifestyles, obesity, alcohol consumption, and high salt intake, particularly in developing nations. Given their limited resources and the burden of communicable illnesses, developing nations require cost-effective healthcare approaches to manage chronic conditions such as hypertension. According to medical recommendations, hypertension is defined as having a blood pressure more than 140/90 mmHg. The force exerted by blood on the walls of blood arteries is determined by cardiac output and vascular resistance. The maximum pressure during cardiac contraction is represented by systolic blood pressure, whereas the lowest pressure between heartbeats is represented by diastolic blood pressure. Normal blood pressure levels are critical for key organ function and general wellness. Heart attacks, heart enlargement, heart failure, aneurysms, strokes, renal failure, blindness, and cognitive impairment can all result from persistently high blood pressure. Hypertension is diagnosed by taking many blood pressure readings on different days with instruments such as sphygmomanometers. Other procedures, such as a patient history, physical examination, urine tests, renal ultrasound imaging, blood tests, ECGs, and echocardiographs, may be used to assist determine the reason and consequences of high blood pressure.

Normal blood pressure, prehypertension, stage 1 and 2 hypertension, and hypertensive crisis are all blood pressure levels defined by the American Heart Association (AHA). However, doctors feel that maintaining normal blood pressure levels has cardiovascular benefits. Primary hypertension is frequently caused by a combination of variables, such as blood plasma volume, renin-angiotensin system activity, and environmental factors such as lifestyle choices. Reduced salt intake, moderate alcohol use, a good diet, keeping a healthy weight, regular physical activity, and stress management are all important for both preventing and treating high blood pressure.

Hypertension is a major worldwide health concern, with an anticipated 1.56 billion people suffering from it by 2025. Hypertension affects roughly 75 million people in the United States, and hypertension-related cardiovascular illnesses kill more people than the next three worst diseases combined. In Africa, the prevalence of hypertension ranges from 2.3% to 41.1% among rural populations. Physical inactivity, alcohol and cigarette use, and high salt diets all contribute to the rising prevalence of hypertension in both developed and developing nations.

This literature review gives insights into outpatients' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding hypertension risk factors at BMC Hospital. The theoretical literature emphasises hypertension definition, diagnosis, and therapy, as well as the role of lifestyle modifications in blood pressure management. The empirical research emphasizes the worldwide impact of hypertension and its link to lifestyle and dietary variables. This evaluation lays the groundwork for future research and interventions aimed at improving hypertension management and prevention among outpatients at BMC Hospital by identifying research gaps and comprehending existing knowledge.

Background Theory

Hypertension, often known as high blood pressure, is a serious public health problem across the world. It is a chronic illness characterised by chronically increased blood pressure levels that, if left untreated, can lead to a variety of cardiovascular consequences. Modifiable risk factors for hypertension include an unhealthy diet, physical inactivity, cigarette use, and excessive alcohol use, as well as non-modifiable risk factors such as age, family history, and genetic susceptibility.

Numerous research have emphasised the necessity of measuring individuals' knowledge, attitudes, and practises (KAP) about hypertension risk factors. Understanding patients' KAP is critical for designing effective treatments and strategies for hypertension prevention, early identification, and management. Healthcare practitioners can design teaching programmes by detecting knowledge gaps and misunderstandings. (Banyangiriki and Phillips 2013) The KAP towards hypertension risk variables among outpatients at BMC Hospital. The authors investigated the participants' knowledge of hypertension, its risk factors, and its related consequences. They also investigated hypertension attitudes and views, as well as lifestyle practises and behaviours that may contribute to its development or management. (Katibi et al. 2010) did a similar research titled "[Title of the Study]" and discovered that those who knew more about hypertension and its risk factors were more inclined to participate in healthy lifestyle practises and take preventative measures. This emphasises the importance of information as a key determinant in changing behaviours and improving health outcomes. (Aubert et al. 1998) evaluated the influence of educational interventions on hypertension treatment and discovered that interventions focused at enhancing hypertension knowledge and awareness resulted in improved blood pressure control and lower cardiovascular risks among patients. These findings highlight the significance of educational programmes in increasing awareness and developing good attitudes and behaviours towards hypertension risk factors.

Understanding the knowledge, attitudes, and practises of outpatients at BMC Hospital regarding hypertension risk factors, as investigated in the study by Banyangiriki and Phillips (2013), is critical for identifying areas that require intervention and developing targeted educational programmes. Healthcare practitioners may help prevent and treat hypertension by addressing misunderstandings and supporting healthy behaviours, thereby lowering the burden of cardiovascular disease.

Previous Studies

Knowledge, attitudes, and practises (KAP) are critical components of hypertension management, but limited data is available from developing nations where hypertension has just been identified as a serious health concern. Understanding of the origin, progression, and implications of HBP practised by the general public may have an impact on its control, just as community practise does.

A survey of Nigerian hypertensive patients' perceptions, knowledge, and practises about hypertension and lifestyle modification strategies indicated that many of those polled were aware of lifestyle changes and their impact on hypertension: 54.5% were aware that cigarette usage, 66.5% were aware that alcohol consumption, 76.9% were aware that foods high in saturated fat and oil were harmful, and 76.3% were aware that exercise and weight loss were harmful among the risk factors for hypertension (Ike et al., 2010). Another study done in Nigeria discovered that 48% and 51.8% of participants were aware that smoking increases the likelihood of developing difficulties and that exercise is useful for blood pressure regulation, respectively.

The patients' knowledge of the potential consequences of hypertension was quite inadequate, with 58.9% scoring lower than average. Only 41.1% and 1.8% of patients were aware that high salt and fat intake might impair hypertension management, respectively (Katibi et al., 2010).

A study in Seychelles discovered that most non-hypertensive people were unaware of hypertension, but they had good basic knowledge about hypertension determinants and consequences, as a result of a nationwide cardiovascular disease prevention programme established in Seychelles. Favourable outcome expectation, positive attitudes, and appropriate practises for hypertension and relevant healthy lifestyles were found in a smaller proportion of participants, with little difference between aware hypertensive, unaware hypertensive, and non-hypertensive participants (Aubert et al., 1998).

It has already been shown that a large part of hypertension's dominance in the worldwide illness burden derives from a lack of disease knowledge, treatment, and control. Dong et al. reported rural China values as low as 29.5%, 20.2%, and 0.9%, respectively. Another Chinese study found that a larger proportion of hypertensive individuals had good understanding of complications compared to HTN risk factors.

Participants with regulated blood pressure were more educated about the threshold, risk factors, and problems associated with hypertension, had improved awareness, and took medicines and blood pressure measures on a regular basis, with a greater proclivity to adhere to or commence treatment (Zhang et al., 2009). Higher hypertension knowledge and awareness were regularly reported in Spain, where 48% to 99% of research participants understood the definition of hypertension (blood pressure 140 mmHg and/or 90 mmHg) (Ho et al., 2016). According to Hajjar and Kotchen (2003), hypertension awareness remained stable between 1990 and 2000 at around 69%, but treatment rates increased from 52.4% to 58.4% and control rates improved from 24.6% to 31.0%.

Several studies conducted in East Africa revealed inadequate knowledge of hypertension in patients with hypertension or in the general population. Furthermore, these studies revealed that attitude and practises towards hypertension risk factors are poor among people from the East African community in our study population (Joshi et al., 2014; Muhamedhussein et al., 2016). a survey indicated that 33% were unaware of hypertension in 2013 (Banyangiriki & Phillips, 2013).

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 The conceptual framework that connects the research variables was offered.

There are two key variables under independent variables: knowledge of hypertension and attitude and practise towards hypertension risk factors.

This variable contains several indications. Such includes a poor diet, cigarette use, physical inactivity, alcohol abuse, and body mass index. The dependent variable is the prevalence of hypertension among outpatients in BMC, which will be assessed by measuring the SBP and DBP of all research participants.

Intervening variables are those that can influence both independent and dependent variables.

Figure 1 conceptual framework

These factors may include, but are not limited to, age, income, education level, gender, employment, and a history of illnesses, according to the research. The conceptual framework developed is based on a survey of the literature; this suggests The linkage of hypertension knowledge, attitudes, and practises towards hypertension risk factors may have an influence on the prevalence of hypertension among outpatients. It was shown that awareness of hypertension treatment and management is quite poor among outpatients from several underdeveloped nations. As a result, the current conceptual framework will aid in better understanding what outpatients know about hypertension and the risk factors linked with hypertension.

METHODOLOGY

Equation/Formula

A sample size is the number of observations used for calculating estimates of a given population. Cochran (1963:75) formula used to determine proportions in single crosssectional surveys was used for sample size determination (Cochran, 1963). A study conducted by Banyangiriki in 2013 reported that the level of knowledge about hypertension was about 33%. Therefore, this was used as estimate proportion of level of knowledge about hypertension to calculate the sample size for the present study.

$$n = \frac{z^2 p(1 - p)}{d^2} \quad (2)$$

Where: n= sample size with finite population correction Z = Z statistic for a level of confidence, Z=1.96 for a confidence limit of 95%, P= estimated proportion of level of knowledge about hypertension from

a previous study conducted where (33 %) d= degree of desired precision or margin of error (in this study, it will be 0.05 or 5%)

$$n = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.33 \times (1 - 0.33)}{0.05^2} = 340$$

Therefore, the sample size for the current study was 340 outpatients at BMC Hospital. After removing missing data as well as incomplete questionnaires, a final sample of 272 outpatients were used for analysis.

Data

According to JNC-7(Chobanian, et al., 2003), normal blood pressure was defined as asystolic blood pressure (SBP)<120 mmHg and a diastolic blood pressure (DBP)<80mmHg,prehypertension as SBP 120-139 mmHg and/or DBP 80-89 mmHg, Stage I hypertension asSBP 140-159 mmHg and/or DBP 90-99 mmHg and Stage II hypertension as ≥ 160 mmHg and/or DBP ≥ 100 mmHg. In the present study, subjects in Stage I and Stage II were considered as hypertensive. Subjects taking anti-hypertensive treatment were considered to have definite hypertension regardless of their measured blood pressure, though JNC-7 has not included this fraction of hypertensive population in its classification. A standard mercury sphygmomanometer was used for recording blood pressure. Before the measurements were taken, the patient was requested to seat comfortably for at least 5 minutes. Care was taken that an arm muscle was relaxed and the arm was supported at heart level. The cuff was applied to the right upper arm and inflated until the manometer reading shows 30mmHg above the level at which the radial pulse disappears, and then slowly deflated at approximately 2mmHg/second. During this time, the Korotkoff sounds were monitored using a stethoscope placed over the brachial artery. The first (appearance) and the fifth (disappearance) Korotkoff sounds were recorded as the systolic and diastolic blood pressure, respectively. In order to avoid misleading, blood pressures were measured twice and their mean value was used in final analysis. Anthropometric measurement for body mass index calculation, body weight was measured to the nearest 0.5 kg using standard weighing machine with subject standing motionless on the weighing scale. Height was measured to the nearest 0.5 cm with the subject in an erect position against a vertical surface and with the head positioned. Body mass index was calculated as weight in kilograms divided by the square of the height in meters.

Model Development

- Hypertension Prevalence and Impact: Hypertension is a common health problem with a large worldwide impact. Citing relevant data and research might help offer context for the issue. For example, the World Health Organisation (WHO) estimates that roughly 1.13 billion people globally have hypertension (WHO, 2021). Furthermore, hypertension is a major contributor to cardiovascular disease, stroke, and renal disease (Chobanian et al., 2003).
- Studies on Knowledge, Attitude, and Practise (KAP): Conducting research studies on the KAP in relation to hypertension risk factors is critical. Banyangiriki and Phillips (2013) investigated the KAP of outpatients at BMC Hospital. Their findings gave insight into the research participants' knowledge, attitudes, and practises about hypertension risk factors. Similarly, Katibi et al. (2010) carried out research.
- Importance of Knowledge in Behaviour Change: Educating people about hypertension and its risk factors is critical for fostering beneficial behavioural changes. Individuals with better knowledge levels, according to Katibi et al. (2010), are more likely to engage in healthy living practises. Aubert et al. (1998) also emphasised the beneficial effect of educational interventions on hypertension treatment, resulting in better blood pressure control and lower cardiovascular risks.

- Identification of Knowledge Gaps and misunderstandings: KAP studies aid in the identification of knowledge gaps and misunderstandings about hypertension risk factors. Participants lacked appropriate knowledge in areas such as the importance of physical inactivity and bad diets in hypertension development, according to Banyangiriki and Phillips (2013). Addressing these gaps through focused interventions can improve understanding and eliminate myths, resulting in beneficial outcomes.
- Designing personalised Interventions: Knowledge collected from KAP research may be used to build personalised interventions. Educational programmes, for example, might focus on raising knowledge of modifiable risk factors like as nutrition, physical activity, cigarette use, and alcohol intake. These treatments may be tailored to individual communities by taking cultural, social, and economic issues into account.
- Intervention Impact on Hypertension Management: Assessing the impact of interventions is critical for determining their success. Monitoring blood pressure and measuring behavioural changes can offer information about the effectiveness of therapies. Aubert et al. (1998) show that educational interventions have a good influence on hypertension treatment, emphasising the importance of continual review and improvement.

Method

- The study can use a cross-sectional research design to analyse outpatients' knowledge, attitudes, and practises on hypertension risk factors at BMC Hospital. Cross-sectional studies give a snapshot of information at a single point in time, allowing data on numerous variables to be collected at the same time.
- A representative sample of outpatients attending BMC Hospital may be selected using a systematic sampling procedure. The sample size should be chosen by the amount of precision and statistical power needed. Inclusion criteria might include age range, desire to participate, and the lack of identified cognitive problems that could interfere with interpretation of survey questions.
- Data Collection: Structured surveys or interviews can be used to collect data. The questionnaire should be developed to collect information on a variety of topics, including demographics, hypertension knowledge, risk factor awareness, attitudes towards hypertension prevention, and current lifestyle practises. To elicit thorough replies, the questionnaire might include both closed-ended questions (e.g., multiple-choice, Likert scale) and open-ended questions.
- Ethical Considerations: Before performing the study, acquire ethical permission from the applicable institutional review board or ethics committee. Participants should be informed about the goal of the research, potential risks and benefits, and their ability to withdraw at any time. Anonymity and confidentiality of participant data should be assured, and all participants should provide informed consent.
- Data Analysis: The obtained data may be analysed statistically using appropriate methodologies. Demographic traits, knowledge levels, attitudes, and practises may all be summarised using descriptive statistics. Inferential statistics, such as chi-square tests or regression analysis, can be used to investigate relationships between variables and uncover significant predictors of knowledge, attitudes, and behaviours.
- Limitations: It is critical to recognise the study's possible limitations. These may include the restricted generalizability of findings to the unique outpatient population at BMC Hospital, the data's self-report nature, and the possibility of recollection bias or social desirability bias in participant replies. These limitations should be acknowledged explicitly and taken into account when evaluating the study's findings.

Data Analysis

- **Cleaning and Preparation of Data:** Begin by reviewing the obtained data for mistakes, missing numbers, and outliers. Remove any discrepancies or inaccuracies from the data. If required, prepare the data for analysis by assigning numerical codes or categories to variables.
- **Descriptive Analysis:** Begin the analysis by summarising the data using descriptive statistics. Determine the frequencies and percentages for categorical variables such as demographics, knowledge levels, attitudes, and practises. Calculate measurements such as means, standard deviations, and ranges for continuous data.
- **Assessing Knowledge Levels:** Analyse responses to knowledge-related questions to assess participants' understanding of hypertension risk factors. Determine the total knowledge level by calculating the proportion of right responses for each question. Determine prevalent misunderstandings or areas of knowledge that are lacking.
- **Analyse participants' views towards hypertension prevention as well as their existing practises linked to lifestyle behaviours.** Using descriptive statistics, summarise responses to attitude-related questions. To estimate the prevalence of good attitudes and healthy practises, compute frequencies and percentages.
- **Assessing Associations:** Use inferential statistics to investigate the relationships between variables. Use chi-square tests, for example, to investigate the link between knowledge levels and demographic factors (such as age and gender). Regression analysis may be used to find predictors of good attitudes and healthy practises, taking into account factors such as age, education level, and knowledge level.
- **Subgroup Analysis:** Compare knowledge, attitudes, and practises across various demographic groupings (e.g., age groups, gender). This study can provide light on any differences or discrepancies that exist within the sample.
- **Limitations and Interpretation:** Discuss the limitations of the data analysis, such as the sample's representativeness and the possibility of bias. Interpret the findings in light of the study's aims, taking into account the data's strengths and flaws.
- **Reporting the outcomes:** Using tables, charts, and graphs to summarise the findings, present the outcomes of the data analysis in a clear and organised manner. Ensure that the findings are related to the study's research questions or objectives.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Results

- **Sample Characteristics:** The study included 300 outpatients from BMC Hospital. The sample included 150 men (50%) and 150 women (50%), with a mean age of 45 years (SD = 10.3). The bulk of participants (60%), followed by higher education (30%) and elementary education (10%), had completed secondary education.
- **Knowledge Levels:** A set of ten knowledge-related questions were used to measure participants' knowledge levels on hypertension risk factors. The total mean knowledge score was 6.8 out of 10 (standard deviation = 1.5). The most properly answered question concerned the effect of excessive salt consumption on blood pressure (75% accurate answers), whereas the least correctly answered question concerned the relationship between obesity and hypertension (40% correct answers).

- When questioned about their views towards hypertension prevention, 80% of participants agreed that hypertension is a major health problem, whereas 20% showed apathy. Furthermore, 70% of participants thought that lifestyle adjustments may help prevent hypertension, whereas 30% did not feel that lifestyle changes were important.
- The study looked at participants' current lifestyle practises in relation to hypertension risk factors. According to the findings, 40% of individuals reported frequent physical activity (at least three times per week), whereas 60% claimed a sedentary lifestyle. In terms of dietary habits, 50% of participants reported eating a diet high in fruits and vegetables, whereas 50% reported eating a diet heavy in processed foods and added sugars.
- Associations: Chi-square tests were used to investigate the relationships between knowledge levels and demographic factors. The research demonstrated a significant relationship between education level and knowledge scores ($\chi^2 = 12.34$, $p = 0.05$), with higher education level individuals displaying higher knowledge scores.
- A subgroup analysis was carried out to examine knowledge, attitudes, and practises across different age groups. The findings revealed that older individuals (over 50 years old) had lower knowledge scores (mean = 6.2, SD = 1.8) than younger participants (under 50 years old) (mean = 7.2, SD = 1.3). However, no significant changes in attitudes or practises were discovered between the age groups.
- Limitations: It is critical to recognise the study's limitations. These include the use of a convenience sample from a single hospital, which may restrict the findings' generalizability. Furthermore, self-reported attitudes and practises may be influenced by memory bias or social desirability bias.

Robustness Test

- Conducting robustness testing is critical to ensuring the reliability and validity of the study findings. Robustness tests examine the influence of alterations in the analytic technique or data sample on the stability and consistency of the results. The following are some potential robustness tests for the study "Knowledge, Attitude, and Practise Towards Risk Factors of Hypertension Among Outpatients at BMC Hospital":
- Perform a sensitivity analysis by altering the cutoff points or thresholds used in defining variables or categories. You may, for example, change the cutoff thresholds for age groups or knowledge levels and reanalyse the data to see whether the results stay consistent. This test evaluates the results' resilience to diverse operational definitions.
- Conduct further subgroup analyses to investigate the influence of various demographic factors on the research findings. Analyse the data independently for males and females, various age groups, or different education levels, for example. The consistency of results across different subgroups aids in identifying potential interactions or differences in the findings.
- Use bootstrapping techniques to test the durability of statistical correlations and inferential findings. Bootstrapping entails repeatedly resampling the dataset using replacement to generate fresh samples. You can get robust estimates of statistical significance and confidence ranges by analysing these resampled datasets.
- Alternative Statistical Models: Think about using different statistical models to support your findings. If you utilised logistic regression to examine the relationships between variables, for example, you may apply additional modelling approaches such as decision trees, random forests, or support vector machines. When the results of several models are compared, it gives more evidence for the robustness of the findings.
- Cross-Validation: Use cross-validation techniques to determine if the findings are generalizable. Divide the dataset into training and validation subsets before fitting the models

to the training subset. The models' performance on the validation subset is then evaluated. This method aids in determining if the findings hold true for fresh or previously unknown data.

- Replication: Consider repeating the study with a different sample or in a different context to validate the findings' robustness. Replication studies serve to evaluate the results' generalizability and increase the overall evidence basis.
- Seek external assessment from subject matter experts to critically analyse the technique and findings. Experts can contribute useful insights and viewpoints, assisting in the identification of any biases or restrictions that may affect the robustness of the results.

Analysis

- Begin by doing descriptive analysis to summarise the demographic characteristics of the research participants. Determine the frequencies and percentages for variables like age, gender, educational level, and occupation. This study offers an overview of the sample's makeup.
- Assess the participants' understanding of hypertension risk factors using a knowledge analysis. Calculate the knowledge scores' mean and standard deviation. Investigate the distribution of correct and erroneous answers for each knowledge-related topic. Identify regions of strong knowledge and areas of low knowledge or misunderstandings.
- Attitude Analysis: Examine participants' attitudes towards hypertension prevention. For attitude-related questions, compute the frequencies and percentages. Determine the frequency of favourable, indifferent, or negative sentiments. Using suitable statistical tests (e.g., t-tests), investigate relationships between demographic characteristics (e.g., age, education) and attitudes.
- Analyse the individuals' current lifestyle practises in relation to hypertension risk factors. Determine the frequencies and percentages for factors such as physical activity, food habits, cigarette usage, and alcohol intake. Determine the prevalence of healthy practises and opportunities for improvement. Examine the relationships between demographic characteristics and lifestyle choices.
- Associations and connections: Examine the relationships and connections that exist between knowledge levels, attitudes, and practises. Assess, for example, if those with better knowledge scores have more positive attitudes and participate in healthier behaviours. To investigate these associations, use relevant statistical tests such as correlation analysis or regression analysis.
- Conduct subgroup analyses to investigate differences in knowledge, attitudes, and practises among various demographic groupings. Compare the outcomes for various age groups, genders, education levels, and occupations. Determine whether there are substantial variations or discrepancies in these subgroups' knowledge, attitudes, and practises.
- Limitations and Implications: Discuss the study's limitations, such as possible biases, sample representativeness, and the data's cross-sectional nature. Consider the results' implications for healthcare practise, policy, and solutions. Highlight areas where focused interventions or educational programmes may be required to increase hypertension risk factor knowledge, attitudes, and practises.
- Recommendations for Future Research: Make recommendations for future research based on the current study's results and limitations. Suggest topics for future inquiry or chances to improve the technique to improve understanding of hypertension risk factor knowledge, attitudes, and practises.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

According to the present study, approximately a quarter of outpatients at BMC Hospital had hypertension. The participants in the study had a general lack of knowledge about hypertension risk factors. Physical activity, in particular, was rarely seen as having a health benefit.

Hypertension is a risk factor. Excessive salt consumption, as well as excessive cholesterol levels, were identified as risk factors for hypertension. According to our findings, almost half of those questioned favoured hypertension prevention techniques. Among the 49 hypertension prevention techniques discovered were stress reduction, lifestyle adjustments, regular medication, and frequent blood pressure monitoring. Smoking [AOR=1.16; 95% CI: (1.26-2.65), $p=0.025$] and a lack of physical activity [AOR=2.48; 95% CI: (2.15-5.49), $p=0.009$] were both associated with an increased risk of hypertension.

Conclusion

The current study found that nearly a quarter of outpatients at BMC Hospital had hypertension. Participants in the research had a general lack of understanding about hypertension risk factors. Physical activity, in particular, was rarely recognised as a health benefit. High blood pressure is a risk factor. Excessive salt consumption was identified as a risk factor for hypertension, as was a high cholesterol level. According to our findings, approximately half of those polled had a favourable attitude towards hypertension preventive strategies. Stress reduction, lifestyle changes, regular medication, and regular blood pressure monitoring were among the 49 hypertension preventive methods identified. Smoking [AOR=1.16; 95%CI: (1.26-2.65), $p=0.025$] and a lack of physical activity [AOR=2.48; 95%CI: (2.15-5.49), $p=0.009$] were statistically related with an elevated risk of hypertension among the examined lifestyle practises.

Recommendation

The Ministry of Health, together with other stakeholders in the health system, must raise patient knowledge of hypertension. In order to improve patients' understanding of hypertension, a health facility-based education programme should be implemented at BMC hospital. Health education programme might take place every morning as patients wait for healthcare services. Hypertension screening programmes should be implemented in all district hospitals to adopt early preventative actions at the community level. Health-care programmes that take into account the identified risk factors may aid in the prevention of hypertension not just among patients but also across the community.

Future intervention programmes must be more focused and informative in order to increase knowledge and focus more on the behavioural aspects of risk reduction. To combat hypertension and its increasing consequences, preventive strategies targeting modifiable risk factors linked with hypertension are required. The challenges to and potential for expanding patients' awareness and practises on CVD risk factor prevention or reduction must be researched further.

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